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Control of T-complex genes by human NOD2.

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We studied expression of the T-complex in the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease, whose major genetic susceptibility factor is the innate immune pattern recognition receptor NOD2. In a heterologous system, human NOD2 could activate the gene encoding t-complex-associated-testis-expressed, Tcte3 in an isoform specific fashion, while it repressed expression of T-complex genes Tcp10 and Tcp11L2.